

INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN PHARMACY: STRATEGY FOR MARKET ENTRY OF NEW DRUGS BASED ON LOCAL MEDICINAL PLANTS

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Relevance: In recent years, the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan has been actively developing towards localization of production and reducing import dependency. Within the framework of the national drug policy, special attention is given to the creation of domestic medicines based on the country's rich natural resources. The territory of Uzbekistan is characterized by a diverse flora: more than 4,500 plant species, of which about 1,200 possess proven medicinal properties. However, only a small portion of these resources is utilized in the pharmaceutical industry. In the context of global competition and the growing demand for herbal medicines, the development and implementation of innovative management in the process of creating new medicinal products based on local plants becomes a strategic task for strengthening the national drug policy.

Purpose of the study: to develop elements of innovative management for the effective market entry of medicinal products created from medicinal plants of Uzbekistan, taking into account the priorities of the national drug policy and global pharmaceutical practices.

Materials and methods: the study was based on the analysis of the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, examination of the regulatory and legal framework for the registration and standardization of herbal medicines, as well as a comparative analysis of foreign experience (EU, South Korea, India). Methods applied include SWOT analysis, marketing research, strategic planning, and a systemic approach to innovative management.

Results: the analysis revealed that the key barriers to widespread adoption of herbal medicines are: insufficient standardization of raw materials, limited production capacities, and a weak system of product promotion in domestic and foreign markets. At the same time, significant competitive advantages were identified: accessible raw material base of medicinal plants (echinacea, yarrow, St. John's wort, horsetail, tansy, etc.), low production costs due to local manufacturing, as well as high export potential to Central Asian countries and the CIS. A model of innovative management strategy was developed, including the following sequential stages: standardization and certification of raw materials, implementation of modern extraction technologies and quality control, creation of "Made in Uzbekistan" herbal medicine brands, application of digital marketing, and establishment of export channels.

Conclusions: the application of innovative management in Uzbekistan's pharmaceutical sector will make it possible to maximize the efficient use of the country's rich natural resources and provide the population with high-quality and affordable herbal medicines. The developed strategy will contribute to reducing import dependency, creating competitive domestic medicines, developing export potential, and strengthening the priority areas of the national drug policy.